

HIGHLIGHTING GREEK TRADITION IN LEARNING GREEK AS L2/FL THROUGH A MULTIMEDIA EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT

I. Antoniou-Kritikou, G. Tsoulouhas, C. Economou

Athena Research Center (GREECE)

Abstract

The present paper offers a brief overview of the role of culture in language teaching and learning. Before the 1960s, there was a clear distinction between language and culture; learners of a L2/FL (Second/Foreign Language) were mainly studying the language in order to read literature and gain access to foreign civilization through their readings. In the 1970s, the emphasis shifted towards communication and foreign language learners were listening to audio recordings, studying spoken as well as written language; after 1980, it has been acknowledged that culture should become part of language teaching and a cultural syllabus has become part of L2 and FL learning in various contexts. Nowadays, language and culture are considered two sides of the same coin; culture teaching is considered an essential part of second and foreign language pedagogy. In this framework, we will define culture in the field of L2/FL in various ways. Acknowledging the importance of cultural learning in L2/FL, we have distributed questionnaires to teachers of Greek as L2/FL to investigate their opinion on issues like the type of cultural material learners need, the role of the level of language proficiency and age of the target groups, the various ways the material can be used in language teaching and learning, the features of the ideal application etc. Based on the results of our investigation, ATHENA R.C. has developed "A year in Greece", a web and mobile application that focuses exclusively on the Greek tradition. The aim of the application is to promote cultural issues to foreigners (tourists, immigrants etc.) who wish to get to know / understand the habits of Greeks as well as to strengthen the cultural identity of members of the Greek diaspora.

How do the Greeks celebrate Christmas and what wishes do they give? What do they usually do on May Day and what are the customs of Kathara Deftera (Ash Monday)?

Users of "A year in Greece" will find the answer to these and other similar questions. To our knowledge, it is the first multimedia educational environment that focuses exclusively on the customs and traditions of Greeks. The teaching material of "A Year in Greece" is organized into 12 sections corresponding to the 12 months of the year. It includes 29 units, each one capturing characteristic snapshots that take place at the specific time of the year and highlight the traditions of Greeks.

In the framework of this paper, we will present the features of the educational environment and will describe the structure of a unit: the introductory text, dialogues, additional information, songs, exercises etc. with their translation in English. Specific examples will be used to illustrate the various components.

"A year in Greece" is designed for self-study as well as for use in classroom settings. For this reason, it is supported by a management system allowing teachers to register users, organize groups of students, and evaluate their work. Finally, learners are engaged in communicative and collaborative activities by using wikis, blogs and forums.

Keywords: web and mobile app, cultural learning, Greek as L2/FL.

1 INTRODUCTION: THE ROLE OF CULTURE IN SECOND AND FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNING

Culture is a complex set of beliefs, values, works of art, literature, history, any kind of social heredity that is transmitted from one generation to the next and differentiates people of one society from another society [1], [2]. In this list, we can add activities and ideas, manners, dress, cuisine, music, the way of life of people, routines like greetings and other everyday habits, songs, as well as festivities, customs etc. which are shared by members of a society [3]. Culture is not a biological phenomenon [1]; it "consists of whatever it is one has to know or believe in order to operate in a manner acceptable to its members" [4], therefore, it is something that should be learned. Language, on the other hand, is a "verbal, physical, biologically innate" [5] phenomenon used as a means for communication and, therefore, for the transmission of all the above to members of a society from one generation to the next. No human society ever existed without developing language and culture.

People learn more than one language for a variety of reasons: to meet interesting people, to get a better job, improve their career choices and their place in global economy. Traveling around the world is very much facilitated if we speak foreign languages. Immigrants and refugees also learn languages in order to settle down in their new homeland. Others decide to change country to find a better job and need to learn the language of their new home.

How should learners of a language approach cultural issues? What should be the role of culture in L2/FL teaching and learning?

Before the 1960s, there was a clear distinction between language and culture; learners of a second/foreign language were mainly studying the language in order to read literature and gain access to foreign civilization through their readings (Allen, cited in [2]). It was in the late 60s that the emphasis shifted towards the importance of culture not for the study of literature but for language learning.

In the 1970s, there was a shift towards a communicative approach and foreign language learners were listening to audio recordings and studying spoken as well as written language through authentic texts; the aim was to foster learners' ability to interact with other learners and the instructor in order to practice their communicative skills in the target language. Once again, cultural issues are neglected since the emphasis of teaching is at cultivating students' communicative competence in authentic environments outside the classroom where they can practice their language skills in various situations.

After 1980, the role of culture in language learning in general and foreign language learning in particular has changed dramatically. L2/FL pedagogy has recognized that language and culture are so closely interrelated that if L2 learners do not have knowledge of the cultural setting of the language they are studying, "... leads to misinterpretation and breakdown in the language communication or it may result into errors and misunderstanding" [1]. "The process of learning a second or foreign language not only requires an individual to practice linguistic forms but also necessitates to become familiar with the culture of target language in order to interpret intercultural communication" [1].

Culture is no longer in the periphery of language learning but becomes an essential part of language teaching and an essential element of the L2 curriculum. Therefore, L2/FL learners need to develop not only their communicative competence but their skills in intercultural communication as well. As Toloza et al [6] maintain, "The goals of foreign language education have, consequently, expanded from the development of linguistic and communicative competence to the development of intercultural skills". Nowadays, the intercultural approach is at the core of L2 and FL research.

Taking the example of English as L2/FL, learners study a rather standard version of the language as FL, but they need to know different things when visiting, for instance U.K. or U.S. At the level of vocabulary, they need to know that in British English, the cloth for the legs is pair of trousers, whereas in American English, it is pants; pants in British English refers to women's underwear. Foreigners who happen to be in the U.S. in late November have the opportunity to participate in Thanksgiving Day. For Americans, it is more than a national holiday with religious roots; it is the opportunity of the American family to gather, eat the traditional meal (turkey with stuffing, cranberries and pumpkin pie) and watch the football games. This is part of the American cultural tradition that residents of U.K., Australia and other English-speaking countries do not share.

As far as Greek as L2/FL is concerned, there is no such need; learners of Greek will cope with a rather homogeneous culture since most native speakers of the language live in a restricted geographical area and have common values, habits, ways of thinking, customs etc. as well as forms of address, expression of speech acts and appropriate topics of conversation [5]. All these are elements that should become part of the official L2/FL curriculum, to facilitate intercultural communication.

2 DESIGN METHODOLOGY

Having accepted that we need to further expose our learners to various aspects of the culture of the target language, various issues should be investigated: What kind of educational material do we need to develop? Are there some cultural topics that should be included and in what order? Are some of them more important than others and need to be taught earlier? Is the age of learners important? Should there be differences among L2 and FL language learners and what is the role of the level of their language proficiency? How important is the use of a supportive language? Taking into consideration the dynamic nature of culture [7], how often do we need to update the cultural material that we provide our learners with? Do teachers need special training [2] to become competent themselves to offer their students relevant activities and material?

Athena Research Center and, more particularly, the Department of Learning Technologies of the Institute for Language & Speech Processing (ILSP) has been conducting research for investigating new ways and means to promote Greek tradition in L2/FL learning and teaching. Within this framework, we have asked teachers of Greek as L2/FL, residing mainly in Greece as well as abroad, to fill in questionnaires about most of the above issues in order to define the features of a multimedia application with cultural material.

We received 25 questionnaires. All our respondents stressed how important it is for learners to study customs and habits of Greeks, thus cultivating their cultural knowledge irrespective of their age and the reason for studying the language. In fact, some of them already search the internet for cultural material for their classes. All respondents stated that they need high-quality multimedia material that they can incorporate in their classroom routine and they really appreciate our effort to provide them with such material in an app. Many teachers emphasized the usefulness of collaborative activities to provoke discussions among participants who share their experiences with the cultural issues of Greek as well as of their mother tongue, in order to promote cross-cultural education. In addition, teachers highlight the need of an inspiring environment for distance learning -as an ideal solution in times of emergency like the covid period. Most teachers maintained that the use of a supportive language like English will facilitate self-learning for all learners, namely tourists who visit (or plan to visit) the country for fun, to immigrants who want to settle down in the country as well as to members of the Greek diaspora, especially for beginners.

Based on the results of our investigation, we have designed, "A year in Greece", a web and mobile application addressed to learners of Greek as L2/FL with English as supportive language. The aim of the app is to highlight Greek tradition to members of the Greek diaspora (adults as well as young children) around the world and to promote Greek customs to foreigners (tourists and immigrants) who wish to understand the traditions of the natives.

The new multimedia educational environment is innovative, for the following reasons:

- For the first time, the teaching material of an application focuses exclusively on Greek customs and traditions,
- For the first time, the teaching material is organized in units corresponding to the 12 months of the year, thus determining the timing of its implementation in the curriculum.

The application has been designed to be used in two ways:

- *by individual users for self-learning*: "A year in Greece" supports self-learning since it constitutes an effective and economical solution for training without time and space limitations. Users can access the material anytime anywhere. In fact, the coronavirus period has shown that distance learning, supported by self-learning educational applications, can provide solutions in times of emergency or special educational conditions.
- *in a classroom setting*: "A year in Greece" can be part of the official curriculum as complementary tool in a classroom setting where Greek is taught as L2/FL. University departments and language centres in Greece and abroad organize Greek language courses addressed to members of the Greek diaspora, immigrants as well as foreigners who are interested to learn the language for various reasons.

3 DEVELOPING "A YEAR IN GREECE" TO HIGHLIGHT GREEK TRADITION

"A year in Greece" is an application developed with the aim of fostering cultural knowledge for all learners of Greek as L2/FL irrespective of their level of Greek and the reason they are interested in the language. The cultural material is organized into 12 units corresponding to the 12 months of the year (see Fig.1). Each month includes 2 or 3 chapters concerning characteristic themes of the Greek tradition. Learners can access the bilingual material by selecting the month (e.g. April) and then the title of the chapter (e.g. April Fool's Day, Easter in a village).

Figure 1. The First Screen.

By selecting a chapter, users have different options to approach the theme:

- **Short introduction to the theme:** An introductory text allows users to understand what the chapter is about, for example, what we celebrate in the Epiphany's Day or the customs of Ash Monday. The text is spoken by native speakers and there is also an English translation.
- **Short dialogues that capture communicative situations around snapshots of the Greek tradition:** To study each dialogue, users have the possibility to:
 - Listen to the dialogue
 - Read the English translation
 - See its illustration

The technique of parallel text alignment developed by ILSP has been used to support users' effort. The original text appears in parallel with its English translation. When users select a segment of the dialogue, both the Greek text and its equivalent in English are coloured (see Fig. 2).

Απρίλιος

1. Το πρωταπριλιάτικο ψέμα

Το έθιμο της Πρωταπριλιάς είναι συνδεδεμένο με φάρσες και ψέματα. Κάθε χρόνο την 1η Απριλίου λέμε αβία ψέματα με σκοπό να ξεγελάσουμε κάποιο φιλικό άτομο που δεν υπάρχει περίπτωση να θυμώσει. Στο τέλος αποκαλύπτουμε την αλήθεια φωνάζοντας "Πρωταπριλιά".

Διάλογος Το ξέρεις; Σύνδεσμοι Κουίζ Ανάπτυξη κειμένου

Είναι 1η Απριλίου και ο Χρήστος θέλει να κοροϊδέψει τους συμμαθητές του. Μπαίνει στην τάξη του αργοπορημένος, έχοντας τυλιγμένο το πόδι του με επίδεσμο.

Δασκάλα: Τι έπαθε το πόδι σου, Χρήστο; Τι συνέβη;

Χρήστος: Να, κυρία! Ήμουν πολύ βιαστικός επειδή είχα αργήσει στο μάθημα του πιάνου. Καθώς κατέβαινα τρέχοντας τις σκάλες του σπιτιού μας, στραβοπάτησα και στραμπούληξα το πόδι μου.

Δασκάλα: Γ'αυτό σας λέω ... Όποιος βιάζεται σκοντάφτει! Για πες μας τώρα, πονάς πολύ;

Χρήστος: Δεν πονάω καθόλου. Σας κοροϊδεύω! Π ρ ω τ α π ρ ι λ ι ά !

Δασκάλα: Οχ! Μας ξεγέλασες, Χρήστο. Και του χρόνου!

It is April 1st and Christos wants to trick his fellow students. He enters the class late, with his foot wrapped in a bandage.

Teacher: What happened to your foot, Christos?

Christos: Well! I was in a hurry because I was late for my piano lesson. As I was running down the stairs in our house, I fell and I sprained my ankle.

Teacher: That is why I always say... Haste makes waste! Tell us now, does it hurt a lot?

Christos: No, I doesn't hurt at all. I fooled you! P r o t a p r i l i a ! (April Fool's!)

Teacher: Oops! You fooled us all, Christos. "Kai tou chronou!" (May you celebrate April Fool's also next year!).

Wiki Forum Blog

Figure 2. The Dialogue Screen (Parallel Texts GR/EN).

By clicking upon the segment, the parallel texts (GR/EN) are isolated from the rest of the dialogue while, at the same time, the Greek text is spoken by native speakers and its illustration is displayed (see Fig. 3).

Διάλογος Το ξέρεις; Σύνδεσμοι Κουίζ Ανάπτυξη κειμένου

Είναι 1η Απριλίου και ο Χρήστος θέλει να κοροϊδέψει τους συμμαθητές του. Μπαίνει στην τάξη του αργοπορημένος, έχοντας τυλιγμένο το πόδι του με επίδεσμο.

▶ 0:11 / 0:11 ◀

▼

It is April 1st and Christos wants to trick his fellow students. He enters the class late, with his foot wrapped in a bandage.

▼

Figure 3: Text Segments in Parallel Alignment, Spoken Aloud with their Illustration.

When used in a classroom setting, these dialogues can give learners the opportunity to practice their speaking and writing skills by participating in classroom discussions on the themes of the dialogues and, then, by writing down similar stories with customs of their birthplaces.

- **Do you know that?** This is where users get additional information that expands the boundaries of a particular theme. For example, in chapter "The end of the school year" users find the wish that we give for "Good luck" in the end-of-year exams and the gesture that follows it (see Fig. 4), whereas in chapter "At Christmas table", there are recipes for traditional Christmas sweets.

Figure 4. Good luck!

- **Songs suggestions related to the theme:** For example, in the chapter "May Day", the user can listen to the song: "Paraxeni protomagia" (Strange May Day) (Dimitra Galani, Manolis Mitsias).
- **Quizzes with multiple choice questions to reinforce users' knowledge:** The system offers learners feedback automatically.
- **Open questions:** Learners produce their texts on a topic either suggested by the system or uploaded by their teachers. For example, in the chapter "It's Mother's Day", users are prompted to write a card to accompany their gift to their mother. Teachers assess the texts and provide feedback to their students.
- **Collaborative activities through wikis, blogs and forums:** "A year in Greece" proposes collaborative tasks in which students are asked to work in a project (write a text of cultural interest, collect pictures, etc.) and prepare a presentation. For example, one of the topics of the wiki is "The custom", where students should give the definition of the entry and write down Greek customs. This is a way to urge students to work collaboratively and practice their writing skills.

To enhance user collaboration in a classroom setting, teachers have access to a user management system, where they can register their students, organize groups, evaluate their texts, create new activities, etc.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, language is inherently cultural, as it reflects cultural beliefs in both implicit and explicit ways. According to Boylan & Huntley [8], language and culture "shadow" each other to such an extent that they are inextricably linked: the meaning of language can often be obscured if there is insufficient knowledge of the cultural norms and values that are associated with the groups or communities that speak the language.

With "A year in Greece", users can learn the language in its cultural context; they acquire cultural knowledge, since they are immersed in a culturally rich environment and are exposed to multimedia cultural material. Users can practice their linguistic skills and acquire cultural knowledge both at their own time and pace (self-learning) as well as in formal educational settings under the guidance of foreign

language teachers. The app offers activities for users to practice their speaking and listening skills by participating in classroom conversations and improve their reading and writing through various tasks on cultural topics that can be carried out in both individual and group situations. Once cultural issues - similarities and differences - have been identified and discussed, comparisons and contrasts can be used to facilitate intercultural communication. Learning about other people's languages and cultures provides students with the opportunity to develop a deeper understanding of their own culture and greater tolerance of people who are different from them.

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